

Co-Designing Citizen Social Science for collective action

Co-Evaluation Codebook

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Abstract

This document presents the codebook for the qualitative content analysis that has been carried out for the provision and reflection of evaluation procedures in a large European research project. The Citizen Social Science Project CoAct was funded by the European Union from 2020 to 2022 and implemented participatory research methods in different settings and regions, driven by civil society groups and organisations. This method paper describes the CoAct co-evaluation codebook used to categorise data for analysis. It includes definitions for theory-driven categories derived from the Citizen Science Evaluation Framework, such as scientific dimension, citizens and individual actors, and socio-ecological and socio-economic aspects. We also present the definitions of empirically derived categories that were inductively coded. The publication of the codebook supports the validation of the claims made in our study.

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1. Background

The CoAct project¹, funded by the European Commission from 2020 to 2022, aims to give citizen groups an equal role in research by actively involving them in the process from design to interpretation of results and their application in concrete actions. With Citizen Social Science (Albert et al., 2021) the project's focus was on participatory research directly driven by citizen groups sharing a social concern. As Co-Researchers, citizens are recognized as local experts and multi-stakeholder collaborations, designated as Knowledge Coalitions, support this process to provide socially robust scientific knowledge that can promote social change. CoAct has brought together and

¹ <https://coactproject.eu>

further developed methods to achieve this goal. One of those methods is Co-Evaluation (Kieslinger et al., 2022a; Kieslinger et al., 2022b).

Co-evaluation is a method of participatory evaluation that involves stakeholders in discussions about goals, objectives, and impacts from the start of a project. It is a process that includes relevant actors in an iterative evaluation practice using participatory methods. Key aspects of the project, such as objectives, understandings of success, challenges, and unintended effects are openly discussed and documented at the beginning of the project and regularly revisited during the research design and implementation, and potentially even after the project has ended. This makes the assessment and intended impacts of the project transparent. Co-evaluation takes a transformative approach as it includes co-creation methods that aim not only to learn about a situation, but also to overcome obstacles, address issues, and find solutions to problems, particularly those related to measuring success in terms of stakeholder benefits and considering marginalised perspectives. The objectives of co-evaluation are negotiated openly and are meant to benefit both science and the participants.

In this text, we describe our approach to analysing the data collected on both the project processes and the evaluation of those processes. We employed Qualitative Content Analysis (Mayring, 2000) to analyse our empirical data. A key component of this method is the codebook, which is used to categorise the data for analysis. In this method paper, we present our codebook. Due to the sensitivity of the qualitative data collected in our research, we have made an effort to present the method as clearly as possible without sharing the actual data. We believe that sharing codebooks and other elements of social scientific methods allows us to verify the rationale for the claims made in our study (DuBois et al., 2018).

2. Method

The present study employed the co-evaluation activities conducted during 2020 and 2022 as the primary sources of data for analysis. Our aim was to understand the concept of "participation in the making" (Chilvers & Kearnes, 2016) and the issues faced by citizen social scientists in this regard. To achieve this, we have employed a range of methods including interviews, participatory observations, group reflection exercises, and self-reflection surveys to track the positions and values of actors over time. Triangulation was then used to combine these different types of data and data collection methods to provide a more comprehensive view on the project processes as well as on the multiple impact pathways such a participatory project creates.

For our data analysis, we used a hermeneutic approach to qualitative content analysis. This method allows us to structure and organise the manifest and latent content of our transcripts and text-based data collections. We primarily draw on the work of (Mayring, 2000), who has been developing this method since the 1980s in the tradition of

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objective hermeneutics and grounded theory. At the heart of the analytical process is the systematic coding of text material. Our focus during the coding process was on a qualitative interpretation of the data, although quantitative analysis was also used in a supportive capacity, such as for visualisations.

Figure 1: Citizen Science Evaluation Framework by Kieslinger et al., 2017

A team of four researchers - all based at the Vienna Centre for Social Innovation ZSI - was responsible for assigning categories to the data material to break down the research question. On the one hand, this work was done deductively using the category system developed based on the citizen science evaluation framework (Kieslinger et al., 2017) as presented in (Kieslinger et al., 2021, 2022; Schaefer et al., 2021; Schäfer et al., 2020). On the other hand, categories also emerged inductively from the data material itself. Coding was performed using memos to ensure a consistent, observable, and intersubjectively understandable procedure and to enable the analysis to be grounded in the material. In a series of communicative validation cycles, we compared our coding with that of the other researchers and harmonised our individual inductive coding into a shared coding scheme adapted to all the material in the corpus over time through discursive agreement. This process resulted in many different categories and subcategories, which were developed across three coding cycles, not all of which can be presented below in full detail. However, we will describe a selection of these categories, which represent particularly unifying as well as particularly divergent aspects of the cases we examined.

To analyse the data, we used the software MAXQDA . Within the software, the "Code System" is displayed as a tree structure on the screen and can be easily adapted and expanded. Codes have a hierarchical structure, meaning that subcodes can be created and then further divided into subcodes of subcodes. The code system in MAXQDA has the following characteristics: A code is a text with a maximum of 63 characters

consisting of one or more words. A code can contain empty spaces and special characters; The number of codes is unlimited; The hierarchical structure can have up to ten levels; Codes can be assigned a colour.

Figure 2: Image taken from MAXQDA website: <https://www.maxqda.com/help-mx20/05-coding/how-to-code> (2022)

3. The Codebook

The CoAct Co-Evaluation codebook includes definitions for the main theory driven categories derived from the Citizen Science Evaluation framework by Kieslinger et al. (2017) - scientific dimension, citizens and individual actors, and socio-ecological, socio-economic aspects - as well as several important categories derived from inductive coding. The subcodes and the respective descriptions allow a more detailed understanding of the categories, their characteristics and the content analysis work. The following list - although not complete for reasons of readability - gives an insight into our coding activities. Italicized are the memos that were attached to the respective codes. Some codes are overlapping - such as “expectations of actors” and “challenges: failures, when expectations were not met” - to cover the range of statements even redundantly and not to lose certain aspects when working with the category clusters in the content analytic process.

Codes for the analysis the CoAct evaluation material

1. Science

1.1. Scientific objectives

To ensure the success of citizen science, it is important to establish clear and transparent scientific objectives that have social relevance and can be effectively addressed through the use of the citizen science approach. With this code we mark statements about the scientific project goals and their communication within the project and beyond project boundaries, as well as statements about the achievement of these goals.

Some key subcodes within this category include

- Scientific objectives > Ethics
- Scientific objectives > Method development or innovation

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- Scientific objectives > Social relevance: *aims and justifications of need in terms of social issues at hand, relation to existing efforts in social change*
- Scientific objectives > Value of citizen science: *knowledge and reputation of citizen science in scholarly realms*
- Scientific objectives > Openness: *remarks about aims of transparency, participation and inclusion in terms of sharing the knowledge produced*
- Scientific objectives > Strengths: *what are the (other) strengths of the project in regard to social science?*

1.2. Data collection and sharing

With this code, we gather insights on topics related to data policy, privacy and data protection, the exchange of data between institutions, platforms, and tools, and the availability of open access to data.

Some key subcodes within this category include

- Data collection and sharing > Openness - *what and how to open, open access, open source,*
- Data collection and sharing > Data policy - *what policies are in place, where are they missing, how are they perceived?*
- Data collection and sharing > Trust - *all dimensions of trust in relation to the sharing of data, such as trust in the data controller, trust in accuracy and transparency, methods, qualifications, security and protection...*
- Data collection and sharing > Informed consent procedure - *any accounts of the informed consent activities, including setup, risks, formats, reactions, ...*
- Data collection and sharing > Methods - *descriptions of the collaborative data collection and analysis process, preparation of data for policy etc*

1.3. Evaluation concept and integration of results

This code collects insights concerning the effect of the evaluation process: what kind of evaluation is it? What are the challenges of “co-evaluation”, which impact dimensions are considered, how are results from evaluation integrated into the project?

Some key subcodes within this category include

- Evaluation concept and integration of results > Evaluation procedures
- Evaluation concept and integration of results > Feeding evaluation results back into the project

1.4. Scientific researchers

With this code we are collecting the description of scientific actors, their roles and functions, their influence on the project, the preconditions that might be required from

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them to be involved. This code is then compared with the “actors” codes, assembling information of the types of roles, norms and behaviours observed in the project

1.5. Cooperation and synergies

Are understood as important benefits for scientists and their organisations, they can come from cooperation with other organisations, projects, initiatives.

Some key subcodes within this category include

- Cooperation and synergies > Strengthened networks, new collaborations
- Cooperation and synergies > New types of science-society connection

1.6. Scientific knowledge and types of publications and other outputs

As a key outcome for scientists and their organisations, CoAct might not have generated many publications yet, but expects to do so? Are citizens involved in the sharing of scientific knowledge and the publications? Which formats are chosen by the project to share scientific outcomes? Are these results taken up by other projects/organisations ..?

Some key subcodes within this category include

- Scientific knowledge and types of publications and other outputs> Methodological knowledge gain
- Scientific knowledge and types of publications and other outputs> New research questions
- Scientific knowledge and types of publications and other outputs> Open Science

1.7. Knowledge transfer

Are the R&I actions ease access to local and traditional knowledge sources, support the knowledge transfer between science, society, policy and civil society organisations? Is this expected to be sustainable?

Some key subcodes within this category include

- Knowledge transfer > Trans- and interdisciplinarity: *how is the process across disciplines and beyond the academic scholarly field organised?*
- Knowledge transfer > Training and education: *remarks on former or present educational activities including attending workshops for data collection or collective data analysis*
- Knowledge transfer > Mentoring: *mentions of mentoring activities*
- Knowledge transfer > Transferability of results: *how can methods and results be transferred to other contexts and domains in the future?*

2. Individual actors (co-researchers, citizens & other engaged actors)

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2.1. Actors

Who is involved as an actor might have a strong effect on the process and outcomes of the R&I actions; thus here we collect the description of actors, their roles, their influence on the project, the preconditions that might be required from them to be involved. These codes also helped us to link different statements to the roles and functions, as well as the motivations actors brought to the project.

Some key subcodes within this category include

Actors > Roles and subject positions: type of actors like co-researcher, knowledge coalition member, facilitator, moderator, or other; responsibilities of that roles; transformation of participants into co-researchers, institutional roles, such as positions in CSOs or NGOs

Actors > Interest and motivations: motivations to participate (and/or to change or stop participation), personal interests, involvement of CSOs, political agendas, etc

Actors > Observations and impressions: codes for accounts of personal observations of participants regarding other participants

Actors > Interrelations between actors: types of social ties, networking activities, etc.

Actors > Benefits, gains > Outcomes and impacts, such as personal awareness, individual learning outcome, personal emotional engagement, knowledge gains for organisation, etc.

Actors > Benefits, gains > Demands: calls to action voiced and/or developed by co-researcher in the co-research process or during the dissemination of results

2.2. Expectations of actors

Actors might be driven to join the project by expectations; which are these, did they change, were they fulfilled?

2.3. Involvement options, activities and phases

Here we label the different options for individuals (other than researchers) to engage with the project, what worked well and what not, in which phases of the research process actors were involved, what concrete feedback we received from participants etc.

Some key subcodes within this category include

- *Involvement options, activities and phases > Collaboration and participation: types of participatory engagement in which project phase*
- *Involvement options, activities and phases > Trust, empathy, respect, security: accounts of aspects of inclusion in participation*
- *Involvement options, activities and phases > Facilitation, settings, project management: code for experiences with the organisation of participation and communication*
- *Involvement options, activities and phases > Using the results: how do the participants and scientists experience the use of the results?*

- Involvement options, activities and phases > Project design, research questions, set-up - methodology: *what type of involvement was possible in the phase of research design and the choice of methods?*
- Involvement options, activities and phases > Feedback: *how were the options for feedback, suggestions, and alternative routes perceived?*

2.4. Communication and material

This code collects insights on the communication with individual actors, which formats and material were used, which language, what was important, is the communication bi-directional ...

Some key subcodes within this category include

- Communication and material > Output types and formats
- Communication and material > Target audiences
- Communication and material > Languages *in co-research and knowledge co-alition, different languages for different outputs*

2.5. Knowledge, skills and competencies

Learning gains are expected to happen for all participants involved in CoAct, it can relate to a better understanding of science and how science works, or to the topic of research (e.g. mental support networks).

Some key subcodes within this category include

- Knowledge, skills and competencies > Expertise: *Assembling and navigating different types of knowledge: how to make sense of transdisciplinary knowledge production*
- Knowledge, skills and competencies > Diversity and team building: *learning about and appreciating the value of diversity and inclusivity, both within the scientific process, the communities, and in society more broadly*
- Knowledge, skills and competencies > Being useful: *making a positive contribution to their communities, as well as “to give something back”, feeling a sense of purpose and accomplishment from being able to contribute to the advancement of scientific knowledge*
- Knowledge, skills and competencies > Curiosity and testing: *developing a sense of curiosity, a desire to learn more about new topics, and the skills needed to apply knowledge to real-world situations*
- Knowledge, skills and competencies > Scientific literacy: *individual knowledge and understanding of science to make informed decisions about personal and social issues this might involve being able to interpret and evaluate scientific evidence, and being able to communicate about scientific issues, applying scientific problem-solving skills to real-world situations and to*

critically evaluate scientific claims that may be presented in the media or other sources

2.6. Ownership, responsibility and behaviour

One potential effect of participation in a citizen science project is that individuals may take ownership and responsibility for the project objectives. This can lead to a sense of agency and empowerment, and may also result in changed behaviour, such as promoting the topic in their social networks or engaging in related activities and projects.

3. Socio-ecological, socio-economic aspects

3.1. Dissemination and outreach

Insights on the dissemination of projects' results to the wider community (not those directly involved in the project) are collected here. Which media and formats are used, what are the key messages that work, which language, what topics to communicate with the broader public, etc.

Some key subcodes within this category include

- *Dissemination and outreach > Synergies and collaborations to support dissemination: synergies from the cooperation with non-scientific organisations, existing networks and civil society organisations to support the broader dissemination of project results. With this code we mark institutions, networks, and other organisations as well as types of collaborations for dissemination.*

3.2. Societal impact and collective capacity

Societal impact refers to the influence that a citizen science project can have on society as a whole. This can include the ways in which the project's findings are used to address social issues beyond improving the public understanding of scientific concepts, or stimulating public engagement with science. A citizen science project may also create societal impact if it brings together diverse groups of people and encourages collaboration and collective action, or if it helps to build capacity within a community. Therefore, collective capacity refers to the ability of those people to work together effectively to achieve common goals.

Here we code the insights related to the societal impact during and after the project of activities that aimed to reach a wider audience or visibility, e.g. increased capacity and resilience of the community/collective, support of sustainable development goals, the ability of participants to collaborate in the wider communities, share resources and knowledge, and contribute their skills and expertise to the social issue in the future.

Some key subcodes within this category include

- *Societal impact and collective capacity > Strengthened collective*

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- Societal impact and collective capacity > Networking - *all types of networking within and beyond the project including the implementation or fostering or challenges of support networks;*
- Societal impact and collective capacity > Inclusion
- Societal impact and collective capacity > Empowerment
- Societal impact and collective capacity > Learning - *the acquisition of knowledge or skills for daily life or job or activism*
- Societal impact and collective capacity > Scientific literacy *on a community or group level such as in school projects or in trainings for policy makers*
- Societal impact and collective capacity > Internationalisation - *both connection to international activities as well as international recognition and embedding of the social issue and actors*
- Societal impact and collective capacity > Help and support - *concrete support measures*
- Societal impact and collective capacity > Attention, understanding and awareness - *including mentions of stigma, discrimination, etc.*
- Societal impact and collective capacity > Goals and means of awareness raising - *concrete aims and measures taken*
- Societal impact and collective capacity > Transformative action - *leading to social change, such as institutional change*
- Societal impact and collective capacity > Citizenship - advocacy - participation: *types of participation and advocacy envisioned beyond the project end*
- Societal impact and collective capacity > SDGs: *any mention of SDG relevant topics or the SDGs themselves*

3.3. Political impact

Political impact refers to the influence that a citizen science project can have on policy and decision-making within the political sphere. This can include the ways in which the project's findings are used to inform policy decisions, shape public opinion, or influence the actions of politicians and other decision-makers. Examples are: the initiation of fostering of conversations between political decision makers and project participants, influence on political agenda setting, changes in procedures in political institutions, increased political engagement for the topic of research etc.

Some key subcodes within this category include

- Political impact > Citizen Science for policy making: *how is CS actually used in policy making*
- Political impact > Pathways for transformation: *first visible steps taken*
- Political impact > Conditions and frameworks for political impact: *what support and regulation would be necessary for CS to create political impact?*

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- Political impact > Indicators: *existing indicators as well as envisioned indicators for social issues*

3.4. Ecological impact

Relates to all impacts in the ecological perspective not yet coded elsewhere, such as observable improvement of the protection of natural resources, reduced pollution, could also be mentions of media articles or reports documenting these changes etc.

3.5. Economic potential

The project and subprojects might have the potential for cost reductions, creation of new jobs, new products, new services, tools ...

3.6. Sustainability

Further codes related to the transferability and wider sustainability of the project results and the subprojects beyond the project end.

Some key subcodes within this category include

- Sustainability > High expectations for change
- Sustainability > Potential for future usage of results
- Sustainability > Continuing advocacy
- Sustainability > New role of Citizen Social Science e.g. in education
- Sustainability > → linked to new networks and collaborations 1.5

3.7. Context

The code where we collect context specific aspects that are not addressed elsewhere, e.g. related to previous projects, specific restrictions ...?

4. Challenges

This code was initially assigned to each of the three dimensions in different orientations, i.e., as scientific, actor-specific, and political or social challenges. In the course of the project, however, it became clear that the code had to be applied across the board, since the challenges in times of a global pandemic, in particular, could not be clearly separated across the dimensions.

Some key subcodes within this category include

- Challenges, tensions, critique > Recruitment and retention of participants: *Engaging and retaining a diverse group of volunteers is challenging, experiences in that regard are coded with this label*
- Challenges, tensions, critique > Project management: *Flexibility, time commitments, specialised skills,*
- Challenges, tensions, critique > Quality control: *Ensuring the accuracy and reliability of data collected by volunteers can be difficult, as they may not have the same level of training or expertise as professional scientists, on the other hand scientists might not be locally knowledgeable enough to recognise biases etc in the data.*

- Challenges, tensions, critique > Data management: *challenges of organising data and making it available for participants or other re-use etc.*
- Challenges, tensions, critique > Ethical considerations: *ethical concerns, such as the protection of personal data and the potential for exploitation of participants.*
- Challenges, tensions, critique > Institutional barriers: *such as limited resources, hindering policies,*
- Challenges, tensions, critique > Funding, legacy and sustainability: *challenges of getting the activities the project initiated funded and making efforts sustainable and creating long-term impacts.*
- Challenges, tensions, critique > Unintended consequences: *what went other than planned, where there any collateral damages, or alternative routes taken not foreseen?*
- Challenges, tensions, critique > Failures: *what did not work out, where were expectations not met, promises not kept, etc.*
- Challenges, tensions, critique > Engagement under COVID restrictions: *this code specifically addresses the COVID-challenges related to engagement or involvement, the new formats necessary etc.*

4. Conclusions

An outcome of the content analysis along the codebook illustrated above was the establishment of project-specific criteria for co-evaluation. This process involved creating the following table that provided an overview of the topics that were subsequently examined in greater detail through co-evaluation during the project.

Dimensio ns	Process and Feasibility	Outcome and Impact	Challenges
<i>Scientific process</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Participant commitment to scientific objectives • Engagement options in times of a global pandemic • Transdisciplinary co-operation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Knowledge production and sharing (incl. publications, conferences, etc.) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Blurred lines of different objectives • Science offers methods more than topics • Scientific questions need to be secondary to social issues

<i>Actors and their roles</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ownership of problem and process • Flexible roles and functions of actors in the research process 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ownership of results and dissemination • Self-experience in different roles • Experience of personal effects 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Resources, temporalities and situated participation • Institutional role pressures • Dynamics and complexity of the process through shifting roles • Feelings of “being evaluated” • Interest and expectation management
<i>Socio-political</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Capacity building and inclusion 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Empowerment by increasing visibility and awareness, also for policy makers • Community building and networking 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Connecting to policy makers • Evaluation of diverse communication and visibility activities • Translatory capacity

Table 1: Co-evaluation criteria of citizen social science case actions (taken from Kieslinger et al. 2022)

Our codebook was a living document until the final analysis. In the process both the theory-driven, deductive codes and the empirically observed inductive codes as well as their definitions were becoming more standardised over time. This facilitated our data exploration not only for the analysis of patterns and the comparison of cases, but also helped us to manage the knowledge to be continuously fed-back into the project research activities.

Furthermore, we hope this codebook will help qualitative analysts in participatory research realms to explore potential routes of analysis as well as allow them to compare and refine evaluation framework concepts and findings across studies.

References

- Albert, A., Balázs, B., Butkevičienė, E., Mayer, K., & Perelló, J. (2021). Citizen Social Science: New and Established Approaches to Participation in Social Research. In K. Vohland, A. Land-Zandstra, L. Ceccaroni, R. Lemmens, J. Perelló, M. Ponti, R. Samson, & K. Wagenknecht (Eds.), *The Science of Citizen Science* (pp. 119–138). Springer International Publishing. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-58278-4_7
- Chilvers, J., & Kearnes, M. (2016). Participation in the making. *Remaking Participation: Science, Environment and Emergent Publics*, 31–63.
- DuBois, J. M., Strait, M., & Walsh, H. (2018). Is it time to share qualitative research data? *Qualitative Psychology*, 5, 380–393. <https://doi.org/10.1037/qap0000076>
- Kieslinger, B., Schäfer, T., Heigl, F., Dörler, D., Richter, A., & Bonn, A. (2017). *The Challenge of Evaluation: An Open Framework for Evaluating Citizen Science Activities*.
- Kieslinger, B., Schürz, S., Mayer, K., & Schaefer, T. (2022b). Participatory evaluation

The CoAct project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 873048

- practices in citizen social science: Insights from three case studies. *Fteval JOURNAL for Research and Technology Policy Evaluation*, 54, 10–19.
<https://doi.org/10.22163/fteval.2022.567>
- Kieslinger, Barbara, Mayer, Katja, Schaefer, Teresa, & Schuerz, Stefanie. (2022a). *Whitepaper on Co-evaluation of Citizen Social Science*.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.7139025>
- Kieslinger, Barbara, Schuerz, Stefanie, Mayer, Katja, & Schaefer, Teresa. (2022). *CoAct D7.4 Final Impact Assessment Report: Evaluation results, overall impact assessment and final reflections on co-evaluation*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.7468546>
- Kieslinger, Barbara, Schürz, Stefanie, Mayer, Katja, & Schäfer, Teresa. (2021). *CoActD7.2: Interim Impact Assessment Report*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.6107394>
- Mayring, P. (2000). Qualitative Content Analysis. *Forum Qualitative Sozialforschung / Forum: Qualitative Social Research*, 1(2). <https://doi.org/10.17169/fqs-1.2.1089>
- Schaefer, T., Kieslinger, B., Brandt, M., & van den Bogaert, V. (2021). Evaluation in Citizen Science: The Art of Tracing a Moving Target. In K. Vohland, A. Land-Zandstra, L. Ceccaroni, R. Lemmens, J. Perelló, M. Ponti, R. Samson, & K. Wagenknecht (Eds.), *The Science of Citizen Science* (pp. 495–514). Springer International Publishing.
https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-58278-4_25
- Schäfer, Teresa, Kieslinger, Barbara, Mayer, Katja, & Schürz, Stefanie. (2020). *CoActD7.1: Impact Assessment Plan*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.6076181>

